

Call for Talents

Build the Future with Neo Forge Lab

The **Neo Forge Lab** is a discreet and innovative laboratory dedicated to developing transformative technological solutions in science and technology. Our focus lies in connecting brilliant minds to explore the unknown and create real-world impact.

We are beginning the creation of an exclusive talent pool for future projects. We aim to attract researchers, scientists, and visionary professionals with advanced training and aspirations aligned with the challenges of the coming decades.

Areas of Interest

We are seeking talents in strategic fields, including:

- **Artificial Intelligence (AI)**
- **Internet of Things (IoT)**
- **Cybersecurity**
- **Smart City Infrastructure**
- **Digital Healthcare**
- **Global Finance Systems**
- **Governance, Ethics, and Sustainability in IT**

Why Connect with Neo Forge Lab?

- Contribute to visionary projects that promote a smarter and more sustainable future.
- Be part of a collaborative community that values ethics, social impact, and innovation.
- Prepare to be invited to transformative projects in collaboration with Neo Forge Lab in the future.

Who Can Participate?

- Researchers and scientists with advanced qualifications (**PhD, Pós-PhD, Master's, MBA**).
- Aspiring candidates for Master's and PhD programs in related fields.
- Experienced professionals or those at the beginning of their careers with innovative visions and an interest in participating in impactful scientific and technological projects.

Submit your CV and showcase how you can make a difference in the future of science and technology: [\[HR\]](#)

Learn more about Neo Forge Lab: [\[LinkedIn\]](#)

Our Invitation:

If you believe in the power of science and technology to transform the world, **join us** on this pioneering journey. Neo Forge Lab is building today the connections that will shape the projects of tomorrow.